

Academic Age Standards Underestimate Global South Career Stages and Research Capacity Building — An Outlook of the Scientific Workforce of Colombia

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The academic age (AA) measures a researcher's experience in producing scientific knowledge. It has an impact on national and institutional policies, including career incentives and funding. However, there have been few studies conducted in global south countries. Our aim was to compare and refine different AA approaches for the Colombian scientific workforce. We used official national data on knowledge products and researchers' assessment. We found that AAs for different academic activities did not show multi-collinearity. Additionally, comparing national rankings with international research career standards revealed significant disparities. This may lead to an underestimation of researchers' capacity building in the global south under AA computation and interpretation standards. Our preliminary findings contribute to discussions about the complexity and necessity of defining career stages, with consideration for diversity and inclusiveness.

1 Introduction

Academic age (AA) influences diverse aspects of the careers of the scientific workforce. Yet, studies validating its relationship concerning scientific-career stages have been conducted mostly in the global north. The aim of this study is to compare and refine different AA approaches and their corresponding equivalence of academic career stages in the global south, focusing on the Colombian scientific workforce.

AA is defined as the time a researcher has been involved in gaining experience in the production of scientific knowledge (Milojević, 2012). This sphere of academic life irradiates upon national and institutional policies (e.g., academic career incentives; funding allocation, open positions) (Kaskie, 2017). Scholars have used the AA to extend many insights on inter-institutional and international mobility, research performance and valuations, collaboration, and the increasing researcher portfolio complexity, to name just a few (Chen et al., 2023; El-Ouahi et al., 2021; Hammarfelt & De Rijcke, 2015; Liang et al., 2023; Lyu & Costas, 2021; Wang et al., 2017; Yair & Goldstein, 2020). This approach, however, is not free of shortcomings. Since the AA studies traditionally have used only research articles or reviews indexed in both canonical bibliographic databases (i.e., Web of Science Core Collection or Scopus), they do not consider other activities of the SW such as teaching, mentoring, or involvement in research and development activities (e.g., spin-off products, consultancy reports).

It is crucial to include these knowledge products, which are distinct from scientific publications, to comprehend the experience of the SW in the global south. This is especially important because global south countries have a long-standing tradition of professionalization, where the emphasis is on training professionals rather than on the production of scientific knowledge (Vasen et al., 2023). Therefore, we ask the following research questions: what other features might unveil novel AA typologies for the Colombian scientific workforce? Is there a correlation between them? Also, how do these AA explore further aspects related to academic career stages of the Colombian scientific workforce contrasting with international standards?

2 Methodology

2.1 Materials

We used two open access datasets published by the Ministry of Science Technology and Innovation of Colombia (MinCiencias) (2022). The complete description of both datasets can be found in the official Open Access data repository (MinCiencias (2022a, 2022b)). The first dataset contains a list of knowledge products of various classes submitted by researchers. Researchers submit their products to endorse their research groups to participate in national research group assessments¹. There are four knowledge products classes, excluding the “no category” class:

- 1) Social appropriation of knowledge and public dissemination of science (SciApp) which includes 61 different products.
- 2) New knowledge (NewKnow), including 53.
- 3) Technological development and innovation (TechInn) with 47.
- 4) Training of human resources (HR) with 20.

¹ National assessments so far have taken place in 2013, 2014, 2015, 2017, 2019 and 2021.

Table 1 shows each knowledge class and their definition. There are 1,318,799 unique products identifiers. Figure 1 reports the top-five product types in terms of intra-class perceptual composition. Overall, HR products composed ~42% of the complete sample, followed by SciApp ~38%, NewKnow ~18%, and TechInn ~2%.

Table 1 Knowledge types and definitions

Knowledge product classes	Definition
Social appropriation of knowledge and public dissemination of science — SciApp	Products involving knowledge exchange and know-how of science, technology, and innovation addressing situations of common interest and proposing solutions or improvements that respond to their realities.
New knowledge — NewKnow	Products which contribute significantly to the state-of-the-art, discussed, and validated, and incorporated into the scientific discussion.
Technological development and innovation — TechInn	Products generating new ideas, methods and tools that impact the economic development and transform society.
Training of human resources — HR	Capacity building activities, fostering the training of new PhDs, masters and professionals (respectively). This includes executing R+D+I projects, which include training and support programs.

Figure 1 Top five most significant knowledge products by classes.

The second data set provides information about the researchers involved in the national assessments (MinCiencias, 2022a). It contains sociodemographic and working information according to the national assessment standards. Figure 2 shows the latest snapshot (2021) of the composition of the Colombian scientific workforce by gender, field and rank. The Colombian national system classifies researchers into four ranks based on their academic training, scientific, mentoring and research performance: *junior*, *associate*, *senior*, and *emeritus*. For instance, the requirements to be classified as *senior* are to hold a doctoral degree or 15 products of new knowledge or results of technological development and innovation activities type A²; a minimum production of ten products type top or type A in the last ten years; and have been a (co)director of four (4) master’s thesis or one doctoral thesis in the last ten years (see MinCiencias (2021) for a complete description of each rank). There are ~38% female researchers, ~59% male. Most of the researchers hold junior positions (~62%), followed by associate (~21%), senior (~14%) and <1% is emeritus. Researchers in social science represent most of the scientific workforce (~30%), followed by natural sciences and engineering and technology (~20%), and medical and health sciences (~16%).

Figure 2 Percentage of researchers by gender, field, and academic status based on the 2021 update.

² Type A products are those of the highest quality. For instance, a Type A research article is that published in a journal in quartile one (top 25% of [SCI and SSCI] or Scopus).

Figure 3 displays a refined glimpse into the percentage of researchers that have produced a certain knowledge product by disciplinary area sorted by the top ten products. The most common product in all areas is the organization of scientific events with quality A (ec_ec_A) and non-academic articles for diffusion or instructional purposes (gc_art). Still, we find some differences by field. For instance, the publication of research articles with quality A 1 or 2 stands out for natural sciences and medical and health science.

Figure 3 Percentage of researchers by product top 10 and area, 2013- 2021.

2.2 Academic age calculation and typologies

We consider two approaches to compute the AA:

- 1) AA-1 is the span of years that had passed since their first research article/review publication, or $A_{v1} = C - t_{fp}$, where C is the current year and t_{fp} is the year of first publication (Radicchi & Castellano, 2013). This approach includes *transient authors*, or those who have just published one research article/review (Milojevic et al., 2018).

- 2) AA-2 is the difference between the year of last and first publication plus one, or $A_{v2} = t_{lp} - t_{fp} + 1$, where t_{lp} is the year of last publication and t_{fp} is the year of first publication (Milojević, 2012). In contrast to AA-1, AA-2 excludes *transient authors*. Therefore, only *multi-paper authors* —or those who have published more than once articles/review— are those who are considered for calculating AA-2.

Both AA-1 and AA-2 were applied to each researcher’s knowledge products limited to the most relevant ones. Here we will consider the top-2 most common knowledge product by class (shown in Figure 1). These are:

- 1) NewKnow:
 - art_a1: research article quality A
 - art_d: research article quality D
- 2) SciApp:
 - gc_art: content generation article
 - ec_a: scientific event quality A
- 3) TechInn:
 - ipp: innovations in procedure and service with quality
 - pi: industrial prototype with quality
- 4) HR:
 - tm_b: master’s thesis-quality B
 - tp_b: undergraduate thesis quality A.

Therefore, the AA is not solely based on researchers’ scientific publications, but it is computed depending on each class of knowledge they are producing. We calculated 16 AA typologies (i.e., 8×2 : eight relevant knowledge products per class by two AA approaches). This reflects a more nuanced and consistent understanding of the AA of each researcher, instead of computing AA within classes, which holds from A1 to D quality products (see Cortés et al. (2024) for insights on AA based on knowledge class).

3 Results

3.1 Academic age types, distribution, and frequencies

In this section, we show the distribution of the 16 AA types, intercorrelations (Spearman rank), and the career stage constructs based on AA approaches and their contrast with the national researchers ranking. Figure 4 (top-left) presents that ~38% of researchers with a record on any AA-1 type have between 1-5 years, with a median of 7 years (IQR=6). Most of the researchers have only one record of AA-1, while the number of researchers with more than one is getting smaller as we reach eight records by researcher (i.e., a researcher with a record in each of the eight AA-1 types of knowledge analyzed are truly exceptional). Figure 4 (top-right) reports that ~76% of researchers with a record on any AA-2 has between 1-5 years, with a median of 2 years (IQR=4). Figure 4 (bottom) displays the trend of the number of researchers with two or more AA’s types decreases.

Figure 4 Top: distribution of number of researchers by AA's types. Bottom: distribution of the count of AA's types by researcher.

Note: art_a1: research article quality A; art_d: research article quality D; gc_art: content generation article; ec_a: scientific event quality A; ipp: innovations in procedure and service with quality; pi: industrial prototype with quality; tm_b: master's thesis-quality B; tp_b: undergraduate thesis quality A.

Count of AA's types by researcher

3.2 Academic age types correlations

Supplementary Fig. S. 1 reports the Spearman-rank correlation plot between all AA types. Figure 5 reports the correlations between AAs types (TechInn AAs were excluded since few researchers have this products in their CV). There is a lack of strong correlation between AA-1 and AA-2, revealing nuances in the application of these approaches across various fields of knowledge production, such as the exclusion of *transient* authors and the requirement of being a *multi-paper* author. Also, when measuring a researcher's expertise in various knowledge-production activities using the AAs typologies proposed, there is no multi-collinearity between them. There were just a few strong correlations ($.6 \leq r \leq .79$) (The British Medical Journal, n.d.) between AA-1 and

AA-2 same knowledge types and classes such as art_a1; tp_b; gc_art; and art_d. There were even fewer moderate correlations ($.4 \leq r \leq .59$) (The British Medical Journal, n.d.) in-between AA-1 types, such as between tp_b and tm_b.

Figure 5 Spearman-rank correlation plot AA-1 & AA-2 types.

3.3 Academic age types and career stages

We synthesized these results via a comparative analysis with international science policy and peer-reviewed literature standards of career stage constructs based on each AA approach and contrast them with the national researchers ranking enforced by MinCiencias, 2021. Previous studies on career stages based on AA-1 classify researchers into four (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2020):

- Junior ($AA1 < 5$).
- Early-career ($5 \leq AA1 < 15$).
- Mid-career ($15 \leq AA1 < 30$).
- Late-career ($AA1 \leq 30$).

In addition, studies on career stages using AA-2 classify researchers into three (Sheng et al., 2023):

- Beginning ($AA2 \leq 12$).
- Junior ($12 < AA2 \leq 24$).
- Senior ($AA2 > 24$).

Figure 6 display the results for AA-1 approach and Figure 7 does the same for AA-2. Supplementary material holds a temporary link with the detailed classification by AA-types. The

cross-validation of national rankings and international research career standards highlights stark disparities, which may cause the underestimation of researchers' capacity building in the global south under the AA standards. This can be attributed primarily to the standardized assessments that specifically emphasize the time gaps between article and review publications in databases like WoS-Scopus.

Figure 6 and Figure 7 are read *horizontally-then-vertically*. Consider the field of agricultural sciences in Figure 6: 55% of researchers were ranked by MinCiencias as *junior*, followed by *associate* and *senior* each with 22%, and only 1% as *emeritus*. Contrasting with the international career stages based on AA-1, 71% were classified in both standards as *juniors*. The disparities emerge when 20% in *junior career* stage are ranked as *associate* by MinCiencias, followed by 9% as *senior*. Even more so, there is no researcher ranked by MinCiencias —either as *associate*, *senior* or *emeritus*— as *late-career* stage ($AA1 \leq 30$) according the four stages proposed for AA-1 (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2020). On the latter point, there are a few exceptions in medical and health science where *senior* ($AA2 > 24$) were also classified as such by MinCiencias. However, despite 21% being ranked as *senior* by MinCiencias, there are virtually nonexistent researchers in the homonym career stages using AA-2 (Sheng et al., 2023).

Figure 6 International career stages based on AA-1 & MinCiencias national rank 2021 by area.

		MinCiencias national rank			
Field		Junior	Associate	Senior	Emeritus
International career stages based on AA1	agricultural sciences	55%	22%	22%	1%
	Junior	71%	20%	9%	0%
	Early-Career	48%	23%	28%	1%
	Mid-Career	40%	0%	60%	0%
	engineering and technology	44%	29%	26%	0%
	Junior	57%	30%	13%	0%
	Early-Career	36%	29%	34%	0%
	Mid-Career	11%	14%	75%	0%
	humanities	65%	29%	5%	1%
	Junior	70%	27%	4%	0%
	Early-Career	63%	30%	7%	1%
	Mid-Career	60%	40%	0%	0%
	medical and health sciences	49%	26%	25%	0%
	Junior	63%	25%	12%	0%
	Early-Career	41%	27%	32%	0%
	Mid-Career	8%	23%	69%	0%
	natural sciences	48%	22%	29%	1%
	Junior	63%	22%	14%	0%
	Early-Career	41%	23%	36%	1%
	Mid-Career	0%	33%	63%	4%
social sciences	58%	30%	11%	1%	
Junior	64%	28%	7%	0%	
Early-Career	55%	31%	13%	1%	
Mid-Career	34%	50%	13%	3%	
Total general	52%	27%	21%	1%	

Figure 7 International career stages based on AA2 & MinCiencias national rank 2021 by area.

		MinCiencias national rank			
		Junior	Associate	Senior	Emeritus
International career stages based on AA2	agricultural sciences	55%	22%	22%	1%
	Beginning	56%	22%	22%	1%
	Junior	34%	15%	51%	0%
	engineering and technology	44%	29%	26%	0%
	Beginning	45%	29%	26%	0%
	Junior	16%	23%	60%	1%
	humanities	65%	29%	5%	1%
	Beginning	65%	29%	5%	1%
	Junior	51%	37%	11%	1%
	medical and health sciences	49%	26%	25%	0%
	Beginning	50%	26%	24%	0%
	Junior	19%	16%	63%	2%
	Senior	0%	0%	100%	0%
	natural sciences	48%	22%	29%	1%
	Beginning	49%	23%	28%	1%
	Junior	15%	19%	65%	2%
	social sciences	58%	30%	11%	1%
	Beginning	58%	30%	11%	1%
Junior	41%	34%	23%	2%	
Senior	50%	50%	0%	0%	
Total general	52%	27%	21%	1%	

Discussion and conclusion

This study compares two approaches for calculating researchers' AA and their corresponding equivalence with research career stages and academic status for the Colombian scientific workforce. The MinCiencias assigns academic status based on merits considering the diversity of activities researchers conduct. Here, we explore to what extent current standards for measuring academic age adapt to countries from the Global South. For this, we use a comprehensive database of scientific outputs for Colombian researchers.

The Colombian scientific workforce is characterized by a strong presence of junior researchers (62%), most of them belonging to the social sciences (>30% of the total), followed by natural sciences and engineering, with women representing 38% of the total. This finding is in accordance with previous studies comparing developing with higher-income countries (Nane et al., 2017), at the same time that disciplinary different must be considered (Kwiek & Roszka, 2022) and ideally must only be used for STEM disciplines.

Both AA-1 and AA-2 and their corresponding career stage equivalents deviate significantly from the MinCiencias national rank, despite we computed AA's based on a diverse set of knowledge

outputs. This divergence can be attributed to the inherent differences in the criteria and outputs considered by each method. The AA1 and AA2 approaches incorporate two different time-lapses in knowledge production. In contrast, the MinCiencias ranking emphasizes both research publications' output and persistency (time-window for each national assessment) and academic qualifications as experience. This discrepancy highlights the multi-dimensional nature of academic careers between global assessments and standardized metrics and national evaluation contexts. This underscores the importance of developing inclusive evaluation metrics that reflect a more complete scope of academic contributions, particularly in the Global South.

Our findings contribute to the current movement for responsible research assessment by expanding the spectrum of outcomes of scientific activities and reinforcing personal capabilities along the research career. This is of special relevance in the Global South, where the emphasis is on training professionals rather than on the production of scientific knowledge (Vasen et al., 2023). The findings of this study also provide implications for the practice of team formation and team management in science (Liu et al., 2023).

Our study might stumble upon restrictions related with a single-country case study. Further stages of this agenda might include comparative frameworks between multiple-country cases. Also, including impact/web-visibility metrics of knowledge products such as research article or patent citations or 'altmetrics.' Our preliminary findings will hopefully contribute to open and enrich discussions about the complexity and necessity of defining the pathways of the career stages, considering diversity and inclusiveness.

Open science practices

The datasets used in this study are Open Access and are maintained and completely described in the official MinCiencias data repository, see references MinCiencias (2022a, 2022b).

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Author contributions

Julián D. Cortés: conceptualization, methodology, software, formal analysis, data curation, writing - original draft, visualization.

Nicolás Robinson-García: conceptualization, writing – original draft.

Zaida Chinchilla-Rodríguez: conceptualization, writing – original draft.

María Catalina Ramírez Cajiao: supervision, funding acquisition.

Competing interests

Authors have no competing interest to declare.

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Supplementary material

Supplementary Fig. S. 1 Spearman-rank correlation plot AA-1 & AA-2 types.

Temporary link to the detailed AA and MinCiencias ranking analysis displayed in Figure 6 and Figure 7:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1rGGfSCSLyL6dK309psoZpBBnQW7J0I4Q?usp=sharing>